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Bahriddinova Nilufar Nasriddin qizi

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

the faculty of foreign languages

a third-year student

Annotation: *The article below is very helpful for every learner of English as it serves to help improving the memory*

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In our century, humanity is so oversaturated with information that even the most interesting news or phrase within a few hours (maximum days) flies out of the head. What can we say about learning: students forget not only the difference in times, but also completely simple words. Let's say right away: we are not giving advice on medication methods of treatment, and we are not going to talk about "magic methods of memorizing 1000 words a day." We will tell you what to do in order to better memorize information.

Recommendations for English classes: mastering the material for a long time

1. Exercise regularly

Stop taking time off from classes. Only with a constant, even load will your brain assimilate all knowledge. Some students believe that it is enough to work out for 1-2 months, remember the basics of English and not worry anymore. This is the wrong approach. No matter how intense and "supermodern" the classes are, a month after graduation you will begin to slowly forget the grammatical constructions. So, if you want to get a good result, practice constantly, improve, develop, communicate with English-speaking friends, watch foreign news and films, read authentic literature.

2. The training load should match your needs.

An intensive English course via Skype is appropriate for those who urgently need to prepare for an interview, travel, business negotiations. It is contraindicated for the rest! You will benefit a lot more from 15 hours of classes per month than from 15 hours of classes per week. Everything around is moving too fast, we are in a hurry, in a hurry. Give your brain some rest: learn a foreign language at a calm pace that's right for you. Do not pay attention to your neighbor Lucy, who, thanks to the new "Hollywood" methodology, mastered the basics of the language in two 3-hour lessons. Imagine what a mess in the head of this very Lucy, and in a week she will completely forget her "basics"! We are determined for a long-term effect?

3. When teaching, use all available methods: Skype, films, videos, songs, books

You should pay attention to all five aspects of language learning: Grammar, Speaking, Reading, Writing, Listening. An integrated approach pays off not only in financial analysis, but also in learning English. In addition, it will not be boring for you to study.

4. Communication with the teacher

Yes, this is a really important point. As a rule, new words and phrases are best remembered in context, rather than simple “cramming”. Our online tutors, teaching conversational English via Skype, have been using this approach for several years now, believe me, it fully justifies itself. In addition, the teacher will encourage you to frequently use new words in speech, which helps improve memory and promotes rapid memorization.

5. Overcoming the psychological barrier, motivation to learn

Perhaps you are studying “because everyone is learning English” or because there is nothing to do? Alas, the lack of motivation for feats does not inspire. We are not going to lecture you and talk about the benefits of learning English. Usually, such notations do not inspire, but annoy people. But before you quit studying and take up ballroom dancing, try a different approach. Think about what really interests you, what topics you would like to study.

REFERENCES:

1. “Learning another language through actions” by James J. Asher
2. “The practice of English language teaching” by Jeremy Harmer
3. [www. ttmadrid.com](http://www.ttmadrid.com)
4. [www. Brige.edu](http://www.Brige.edu).
5. www.teflacademy.com

